

Learning objectives

Workshop 1: Population / physiologically based pharmacokinetic modelling

This workshop will introduce the main concepts of pharmacokinetic modelling approaches via lectures and interactive hands-on sessions during which the participants will have the opportunity to explore modelling software such as the Monolix suite for Population Pharmacokinetic Modelling (PopPK) and PKSim/SimCYP for Physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling.

At the end of this workshop, the attendees will be able to:

1. Describe the mathematical and physiological concepts behind PopPK and PBPK models.
2. Outline the general workflow and methodologies for the development and validation of PK models.
3. Give examples of applications of these approaches in the contexts of personalized medicine, especially for vulnerable populations (pediatric, geriatric, etc.) and for drug-drug interactions evaluation.

Workshop 2: Pharmacogenetic variants testing using real time PCR

At the end of this workshop, the attendees of the workshop will be able to

1. Outline the requirements for a candidate gene variant testing
2. Describe the process of candidate variant genotyping using real time PCR instrument
3. Operate the instrumentation
4. Specify the required controls for a proper genotyping experiment
5. Using genotype results for personalized dose modifications

Workshop 3: Exome sequencing data analyses

At the end of this workshop participants will be able to

1. Recognize the steps and process of exome sequencing data analyses
2. Review and critically apprise the exome sequencing data analyses presented in the exome wide association studies
3. propose and design the exome sequencing data analyses strategies together with a bioinformatician

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Workshop 1: Pre-Conference workshop: Population and Physiologically based Pharmacokinetic modelling 2024

Prof. Youssef Daali, Dr. Khalil Ben Hassine (Geneva University Hospitals, Switzerland), and Dr. Surulivel Rajan M (Manipal College of Pharmaceutical Sciences)

The aim of the workshop is to introduce participants notions of pharmacometrics (PopPK and PBPK)

Objective: discover pharmacometrics software, learn how to use them, obtain pharmacokinetic parameters and interpret the results obtained.

Planning: Lecture and practice will be mixed around clinical cases and different approaches will be studied:

- Non-compartmental analysis approach (NCA, PKanalix)
- Population approach (PopPK, Monolix)
- Physiology-based approach (PKSim, PBPK)

We ask participants to bring their own computers with the softwares installed in order to be able to practice.

The course material and hands-on instructions will be made available during the workshop.

Workshop schedule (provisional):

- 9:00-9:30: Introductions and Learning objectives
- 9:30-10:30: Introduction to PBPK modeling (Interactive lecture by Dr. Khalil)
- 10:30-10:50: Tea Break
- 10:50-11:30: Hands-on session PBPK (PKSim)
- 11:30- 12:30: Introduction to NCA and PopPK modeling (Dr. Youssef and Dr. Rajan)
- 12:30 – 13:30: Lunch Break
- 13:30-14:30: Interactive hands-on session NCA (PKanalix) and PopPK (Monolix)-Dr. Rajan and Dr. Youssef
- 14:30-15:00: Application of population pharmacokinetics to the therapeutic drug monitoring of targeted anticancer agents; Talk by Dr. Nicole Widmer
- 15:00-15:45: Q & A session all speakers and participants

Instructions before the workshop:

Please start the software installation at least one week before the workshop day, in order to have sufficient time to obtain the Monolix license and in case of troubleshooting.

1. Instructions for Monolix and PKanalix installation (Monolix suite):
 - download and install PKanalix and Monolix software from the website : <https://lixoft.com/downloads/>
 - Request an academic license from the same link (free of charge). The academic license key will be normally sent to you within two business days.
 - Please open Monolix and PKanalix software and run a test if possible following the instructions below:
https://lixoft.com/downloads/how-to-see-that-the-applications-are-well-installed/?_ga=2.131808843.517321964.1690355887-848994892.1690355887&_gl=1*9knqw6*_ga*ODQ0T0k0ODkyLjE2OTAzNTU4ODc.*_ga_4GW4HZKV1L*MTY5MDM1NTg4Ni4xLjEuMTY5MDM1NjEwOC4wLjAuMA..*_ga_CVKZ99PT6W*MTY5MDM1NTg4Ni4xLjEuMTY5MDM1NjEwOC4wLjAuMA
 - Check the troubleshooting page if you have any problem during download, installation, or run.
2. Instructions for PKSim installation:

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- Go to <https://github.com/Open-Systems-Pharmacology/Suite/releases/tag/v11.3>
- Click on “Full setup” and “Gene expression database (human)”
- Install the software: Follow the instructions provided in the link below, including the setup of the gene expression database:

<https://docs.open-systems-pharmacology.org/open-systems-pharmacology-suite/getting-started>

Workshop 2: Schedule and learning material

Problem 1: Predict the appropriate clopidogrel therapy for a patient of Indian ethnic origin based on their *CYP2C19*3* genotype, considering the possible phenotypes and their impact on clopidogrel metabolism. Please refer to pg.no 11 for the table to complete the results.

#**Problem 2 :** Predict the appropriate clopidogrel therapy for a patient of Indian ethnic origin based on their *DPYD*2A* genotypes, considering the possible phenotypes and their impact on 5-Flurouracil metabolism.

Steps:

- A) Obtain informed consent
- B) Collect blood samples to extract germ-line DNA
- C) Perform DNA extraction and check the quality of DNA.
- D) Genotype for the selected variant using allele-discrimination assay.

Genotyping of CYP2C19 (rs4986893) polymorphism by using allele discrimination assay using Real-Time PCR method.

Enzyme: CYP2C19

Substrates: E.g. Clopidogrel. For more details: <http://medicine.iupui.edu/clinpharm/ddis/main-table/>

Importance of this allele: It is also known as CYP2C19*3, is an important genetic polymorphism of the CYP2C19 gene that has significant implications for drug metabolism (clopidogrel). It is characterized by a G>A transition at position 636 of the CYP2C19 gene (636G>A). This single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) results in a loss-of-function allele, which means it reduces the enzyme's ability to metabolize certain drugs. It is generally more common in Asian populations compared to other ethnic groups.

Please refer to: <https://www.pharmvar.org/> for details on the CYP allele and other pharmacogene nomenclature.

Please refer to the lecture notes of Pharmacogenetics from the course.

General instructions: *Pipetting, Centrifugation.*

DNA extraction:

Lysis of cells is a common step in most DNA extraction protocols, and it is commonly achieved through the use of detergents and enzymes. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and Triton™ X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis, MO, USA) are examples of popular detergents used to solubilize cell membranes. Enzymes are also combined with detergents to target cell surface or cytosolic

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components. Proteinase K is an enzyme used to cleave glycoproteins and inactivate RNases and DNases. Other denaturants such as urea, guanidinium salts, and chemical chaotropes are used to disrupt cells and inactivate cellular enzymes, but these can impact on quality and nucleic acid yield.

DNA precipitation is achieved by adding high concentrations of salt to DNA-containing solutions, as cations from salts such as ammonium acetate counteract repulsion caused by the negative charge of the phosphate backbone. A mixture of DNA and salts in the presence of solvents like ethanol (final concentrations of 70%–80%) or isopropanol (final concentrations of 40%–50%) causes nucleic acids to precipitate. Some protocols include washing steps with 70% ethanol to remove excess salt from DNA. Finally, nucleic acids are resuspended in water or TE buffer (10 mM Tris, 1 mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid [EDTA]). TE buffer is commonly used for long-term DNA storage because it prevents it from being damaged by nucleases, inadequate pH, heavy metals, and oxidation by free radicals. Tris provides a safe pH of 7–8, and EDTA chelates divalent ions used in nuclease activity and counteracts oxidative damage from heavy metals.

Table 1. DNA extraction methods commonly used for extraction from whole blood samples

DNA extraction method (main category)	DNA extraction method (subcategory)	DNA extraction protocol stage			
		Cell lysis	Denaturation of nucleoproteins/ inactivation of cellular enzymes	Removal of contaminants	DNA precipitation
Solution-based DNA extraction methods	Salting out methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDS • SDS/proteinase K • Triton X-100 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proteinase K • Laundry powder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potassium acetate • Sodium acetate • Sodium chloride 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethanol • Isopropanol
	Organic solvent/ chaotropes methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDS • SDS/proteinase K 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guanidine thiocyanate • Phenol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phenol • Phenol–chloroform • Phenol–chloroform, isoamyl alcohol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sodium acetate/ ethanol • Sodium acetate/ isopropanol
Solid-phase DNA extraction methods	Glass milk/silica resin methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDS • Triton X-100 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guanidine thiocyanate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Glass milk (silica in chaotropic buffer) • Silica matrix • Diatomaceous earth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethanol • Isopropanol
	Anion exchange methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heat 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chelex • Chelex/proteinase K 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chelex 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
	Magnetic beads methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sodium chloride/ polyethylene glycol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Magnetic beads

Abbreviations: DNA, deoxyribonucleic acid; N/A, not applicable; SDS, sodium dodecyl sulfate.

Procedure:

DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (cat. nos. 69504 and 69506)

Notes before starting

- Perform all centrifugation steps at room temperature (15–25°C).
- Redissolve any precipitates in Buffer AL and Buffer ATL.
- Preheat an incubator to 56°C.

1. Nonnucleated blood: Pipet 20 µl proteinase K into a 1.5 ml or 2 ml microcentrifuge tube. Add 50–100 µl anticoagulant-treated blood. Adjust volume to 220 µl with PBS.

2. Add 200 µl Buffer AL. Mix thoroughly by vortexing. Incubate blood samples at 56°C for 10 min.

3. Add 200 µl ethanol (96–100%). Mix thoroughly by vortexing.

4. Pipet the mixture into a DNeasy Mini spin column placed in a 2 ml collection tube. Centrifuge at $\geq 6000 \times g$ (8000 rpm) for 1 min. Discard the flow-through and collection tube.

- ↓
5. Place the spin column in a new 2 ml collection tube. Add 500 µl Buffer AW1. Centrifuge for 1 min at $\geq 6000 \times g$. Discard the flow-through and collection tube.
- ↓
6. Place the spin column in a new 2 ml collection tube, add 500 µl Buffer AW2, and centrifuge for 3 min at 20,000 x g (14,000 rpm). Discard the flow-through and collection tube.
- ↓
7. Transfer the spin column to a new 1.5 ml or 2 ml microcentrifuge tube.
- ↓
8. Elute the DNA by adding 200 µl Buffer AE to the center of the spin column membrane. Incubate for 1 min at room temperature (15–25°C). Centrifuge for 1 min at $\geq 6000 \times g$.
- ↓
9. Optional: Repeat step 8 for increased DNA yield.

DNA quantity and Purity check: Concentration, yield and purity of a DNA using absorbance method (Nanodrop), fluorescent DNA-binding dye (Qubit Fluorimeter) and agarose gel electrophoresis (or tape station)

DNA yield can be assessed using various methods including absorbance (optical density), use of fluorescent DNA-binding dyes or agarose gel electrophoresis.

a) Absorbance Methods

The most common technique to determine DNA yield and purity is measurement of absorbance. By using a spectrophotometer equipped with a UV lamp, UV-transparent cuvettes and a solution of purified DNA. Absorbance readings are performed at 260nm (A_{260}) where DNA absorbs light most strongly, and the number generated allows one to estimate the concentration of the solution. To ensure the numbers are useful, the A_{260} reading should be within the instrument's linear range (generally 0.1–1.0). DNA concentration is estimated by measuring the absorbance at 260nm, adjusting the A_{260} measurement for turbidity (measured by absorbance at 320nm), multiplying by the dilution factor, and using the relationship that an A_{260} of 1.0 = 50µg/ml pure dsDNA.

$$\text{Concentration } (\mu\text{g/ml}) = (A_{260} \text{ reading} - A_{320} \text{ reading}) \times \text{dilution factor} \times 50\mu\text{g/ml}$$

Total yield is obtained by multiplying the DNA concentration by the final total purified sample volume.

$$\text{DNA yield } (\mu\text{g}) = \text{DNA concentration} \times \text{total sample volume (ml)}$$

However, DNA is not the only molecule that can absorb UV light at 260nm. Since RNA also has a great absorbance at 260nm, and the aromatic amino acids present in protein absorb at 280nm, both contaminants, if present in the DNA solution, will contribute to the total measurement at 260nm. Additionally, the presence of guanidine will lead to higher 260nm absorbance. This means that if the A_{260} number is used for calculation of yield, the DNA quantity may be overestimated.

The most common purity calculation is the ratio of the absorbance at 260nm divided by the reading at 280nm. Good-quality DNA will have an A_{260}/A_{280} ratio of 1.7–2.0. A reading of 1.6 does not render the DNA unsuitable for any application, but lower ratios indicate more contaminants are present. The ratio can be calculated after correcting for turbidity (absorbance at 320nm).

$$\text{DNA purity } (A_{260}/A_{280}) = (A_{260} \text{ reading} - A_{320} \text{ reading}) \div (A_{280} \text{ reading} - A_{320} \text{ reading})$$

Strong absorbance around 230nm can indicate that organic compounds or chaotropic salts are present in the purified DNA. A ratio of 260nm to 230nm can help evaluate the level of salt carryover in the purified DNA. The lower the ratio, the greater the amount of thiocyanate salt is present, for example. As a guideline, the A_{260}/A_{230} is best if greater than 1.5.

Procedure (NanoDrop 2.0):

1. Switch on the instrument, and the software connected to the instrument.
2. Select measure dsDNA
3. Place 2 uL of buffer i.e. used to elute DNA as blank and set the blank
4. Place 2uL of DNA sample and measure the absorbance on NanoDrop apparatus with proper sample ID entered
5. Measure the concentration.
6. Write down the concentration and A_{260}/A_{280} ratio
7. After measuring all the concentrations with properly entered sample IDs, export the results in an excel sheet.

b) Fluorescence Methods

Fluorescence methods are more sensitive than absorbance, particularly for low-concentration samples, and the use of DNA-binding dyes allows more specific measurement of DNA than spectrophotometric methods allow. Hoechst bisbenzimidazole dyes, **PicoGreen®** and QuantiFluor™ dsDNA dyes selectively bind double-stranded DNA. Fluorescence measurements are set at excitation and emission values that vary depending on the dye chosen. The concentration of unknown samples is calculated based on comparison to a standard curve generated from samples of known DNA concentration.

Materials required for fluorescence methods are: a fluorescent DNA binding dye, a fluorometer to detect the dyes, and appropriate DNA standards.

Procedure (Qubit):

NOTE: Ensure that all assay reagents are at room temperature before you begin.

1. Set up one Assay Tube for each user sample and one Assay Tube for the standard.
2. Prepare the Qubit® Working Solution by diluting the Qubit® reagent 1:200 in Qubit® buffer. Prepare 200 µL of Working Solution for the standard and each sample.
3. Prepare the Assay Tubes (0.5mL PCR tubes) according to the table below.
4. Vortex all tubes for 2–3 seconds.
5. Incubate the tubes for 2 minutes at room temperature.
6. Insert the tubes in the Qubit® Fluorometer and take readings.

Notes: -----

	Qubit Working Solution (1x) – DNA sample	Qubit Working Solution (for N samples+standard)	User Sample Assay Tube (1X)	Standard Assay Tube (1X)
<i>Qubit Buffer</i>	<i>199 uL</i>		/	/
<i>Qubit dsDNA BR reagent 200x</i>	<i>1uL</i>		/	/
Qubit Working Solution	/	/	198uL	190uL
Volume of User Sample (DNA sample or standard)	/	/	2uL	10uL
Total Volume	200 uL		200uL	200uL

Results:

DNA sample ID	Concentration- Qubit (ng/ml)	Concentration- Nanodrop (ng/mL)	Sample purity (A260/A280)	Comparison: CV (%)

Comment the quality and concentrations by using two different methods of your DNA sample:

c) Agarose Gel Electrophoresis

Agarose gel electrophoresis is another way to quickly estimate DNA concentration. To use this method, a horizontal gel electrophoresis tank with an external power supply, analytical-grade agarose, an appropriate running buffer (e.g., 1X TAE) and an intercalating DNA dye (e.g. Sybr Safe) along with appropriately sized DNA standards are required. A sample of the isolated DNA is loaded into a well of the agarose gel and then exposed to an electric field. The negatively charged DNA backbone migrates toward the anode. Since small DNA fragments migrate faster, the DNA is separated by size. The percentage of agarose in the gel will determine what size range of DNA will be resolved with the greatest clarity. Any RNA, nucleotides and protein in the sample migrate at different rates compared to the DNA so the band(s) containing the DNA will be distinct.

Concentration and yield can be determined after gel electrophoresis is completed by comparing the sample DNA intensity to that of a DNA quantitation standard. For example, if a 2µl sample of undiluted DNA loaded on the gel has the same approximate intensity as the 100ng standard, then the solution concentration is 50ng/µl (100ng divided by 2µl). Standards used for quantitation should be labeled as such and be the same size as the sample DNA being analyzed. In order to visualize the DNA in the agarose gel, staining with an intercalating dye such as ethidium bromide or SYBR® Safe is required. Because ethidium bromide is a known mutagen, precautions need to be taken for its proper use and disposal. Tape station is an instrument that can provide the similar analysis without the buffer tanks. Please refer to the material here: <https://www.agilent.com/en/product/tapestation-automated-electrophoresis/tapestation-instruments/4200-tapestation-system-228263#productdetails>

Notes: -----

Genotyping of CYP2C19 variant or single nucleotide polymorphism (C__27861809_10 /rs4986893)

Overview of TaqMan® Probe-Based Chemistry (ThermoFischer scientific)

Genotyping of CYP2C19 polymorphism rs4986893 of unknown samples and one positive control with the known genotype will be performed by using the TaqMan Drug Metabolism Genotyping Assay.

The assay consists of:

- Two sequence-specific primers for amplifying the region with this variant (polymorphism) in CYP2C19 gene
- Two allele-specific TaqMan® MGB probes for detecting the alleles for the specific polymorphism of interest

Each allele-specific TaqMan MGB probe has:

- A reporter dye at its 5' end
 - VIC® dye is linked to the 5' end of the Allele 1 probe.
 - FAM™ dye is linked to the 5' end of the Allele 2 probe.

The **Allele 1 VIC dye-labeled probe** corresponds to the first nucleotide inside the square brackets of the context sequence.

The **Allele 2 FAM dye-labeled probe** corresponds to the second nucleotide inside the square brackets of the context sequence.

For the context CYP2C19 sequence ACATCAGGATTGTAAGCACCCCCTG[A/G]ATCCAGGTAAGGCCAAGTTTTTGC, the VIC dye-labeled probe binds to the allele containing A and the FAM dye-labeled probe binds to the allele containing G.

- A minor groove binder (MGB), which increases the melting temperature (Tm) for a given probe length, allows the design of shorter probes. The presence of the MGB results in greater differences in Tm values between matched and mismatched probes. These differences produce more robust allelic discrimination.
- A nonfluorescent quencher (NFQ) at its 3' end which allows detection of reporter dye contributions with greater sensitivity.

During PCR:

- Each TaqMan MGB probe anneals specifically to its complementary sequence between the forward and reverse primer sites.
- When the oligonucleotide probe is intact, the proximity of the quencher dye to the reporter dye causes the reporter dye signal to be quenched.
- AmpliTaq Gold® DNA polymerase extends the primers bound to the genomic DNA template.
- AmpliTaq Gold DNA polymerase (a 5' nuclease) cleaves probes that are hybridized to the target sequence.
- When the hybridized probes are cleaved by AmpliTaq Gold DNA polymerase, the quencher dye is separated from the reporter dye, increasing the fluorescence of the reporter dye. Therefore, the fluorescence signal generated by PCR amplification indicates which alleles are present in the sample.

In TaqMan assays, fluorescence from nonspecifically bound probes is reduced because nucleotide mismatches between a probe and a sequence reduce the chances that the probe will be cleaved. The probe's short length means a one base-pair mismatch has a larger negative effect on the binding than for a longer probe. The mismatched probe does not bind tightly to the allele, allowing the AmpliTaq Gold® DNA polymerase to displace the probe without cleaving the dye.

Notes: -----

Figure 1: Schematic depiction of a TaqMan® Drug Metabolism Genotyping Assay

TaqMan Drug Metabolism Genotyping Assays are read at the PCR endpoint. DNA samples on 96-well plates are genotyped simultaneously. Genotype calls for individual samples are made by plotting the normalized intensity of the reporter dyes in each sample well on an allelic discrimination plot. An algorithm in the data analysis software assigns individual sample data to a particular cluster and makes the genotype calls.

Figure 2. Example of an allelic discrimination plot for a TaqMan® Drug Metabolism Genotyping Assay

Procedure:

Prepare master-mix mixture in 1.5 mL tube using TaqMan Universal PCR Master Mix (which contains the DNA polymerase enzyme, dNTPs, MgCl₂, buffer to maintain PH) and TaqMan Drug Metabolism Assay mix specific for this variant (with specific primers and probes). Aliquot required volume (total reaction volume is 20 uL) it into the 96th -well plate and add the DNA sample. Each sample will be measured in duplicates and one positive control with the known genotype will be used. Include also negative control without any DNA sample to control the possible contamination of reagents.

1. Thaw and mix the reagents
2. Calculate the number of reactions
3. Prepare the PCR reaction mix in 1.5mL microcentrifuge tube according to calculated volumes in the table below
4. Prepare the reaction plate for the each sample with the unknown genotype, positive and negative control in duplicates, the way it was designed /to be designed on the SteponePlus software.
5. After preparation, seal with transparent lid, briefly centrifuge not to have air bubbles at the bottem of the well.

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Components	1 sample	N samples + 1 (to account pipetting error)
TaqMan Universal PCR Master Mix (2X)	10	
TaqMan Drug Metabolism probe (20X) C__25625805_10; rs1799853	1	
DNA sample (diluted)*	1	
RNase-free water	8	
Total Volume	20uL	

* To be added to the plate only at the end. DNA concentrations of all samples and positive controls that are to be genotyped in the same plate must be uniformly diluted to the same concentration (for e.g. 25ng/uL or 10 ng/uL or 50 ng/uL). Based on the concentration you will decide the volume to be added to each well.

Template (*note down the plate layout*):

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A												
B												
C												
D												
E												
F												
G												
H												

6. Run the samples on StepOne Real-Time PCR machine (*write down the cycle conditions below*)

Notes: -----

7. Allelic discrimination analysis

Results

- a) Draw allelic discrimination plot and genotype your sample
- b) Observe and mention the Ct values of your samples , NTCs, and positive controls
- c) Observe multiple component plots
- d) Notedown all genotype results:

DNA sample	Genotype
Positive control 1, 2	
Negative control	

Comments

(Comment your genotyping graph and the quality of the genotyping, what does the result mean for the patient):

Exercise: Personalization of clopidogrel dosing based on *CYP2C19* genotyping – hypothetical exercise (only for training purpose)

Reference: Three Ranges of Expected Maintenance clopidogrel Doses based on *CYP2C19* Genotypes, adapted from the FDA drug label given below.

Genotype	Phenotype	Dose recommendation	Treatment protocol
1/*1	Extensive Metabolizer	75 mg daily	Standard treatment
*1/*2 or *1/*3	Heterozygous / Intermediate Metabolizer	Consider higher dose (e.g., 150 mg daily) or alternative therapy	Adjust treatment based on clinical judgement
*2/*2 or *2/*3	Poor Metabolizer	Avoid clopidogrel; consider alternative therapy	High risk of adverse events with standard dose
*3/*3, *1/*4, *1/*6, *1/*8	Poor Metabolizer	Avoid clopidogrel; consider alternative therapy	Very high risk of adverse events
*17 carrier	Ultrarapid or Rapid Metabolizer	No specific recommendation	Increased active metabolite formation; lower on-treatment platelet reactivity

Hypothetical Scenario:

1) What is the Genotype for *CYP2C19* locus you found in your sample: GG (*1*1)
Select the genotype and diplotype AG (*1*3)
AA(*3*3)

2) Now predict the clopidogrel maintenance dose for the candidate with the tested (found in your experiment) genotype. Consider all the possible *CYP2C19* genotypes.

CYP2C19 genotype----- (considering that *2 is common in Indians, and we tested for only *3, but in reality *2 allele also must be tested in Indians, and other alleles in other ethnicities and other genes)

Clopidogrel dose range (mg) based on the genotype or any other recommendation?	<i>CYP2C19</i> genotype*3	<i>CYP2C19</i> genotype for *2	Common <i>CYP2C19</i> diplotype considering *2 and *3 alleles (derive)
	GG	GA	
	AG	GA	
	AA	GA	

Please refer to the following for more details:

1. CPIC Guidelines for clopidogrel dosing.

<https://files.cpicpgx.org/data/guideline/publication/clopidogrel/2022/35034351.pdf>

2. Clopidogrel Therapy and the Genotypes *CYP2C19*. NCBI Book summaries:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK84114/>

Table 3 Antiplatelet therapy recommendations based on CYP2C19 phenotype when considering clopidogrel for neurovascular indications^a

CYP2C19 phenotype ^b	Implications for phenotypic measures	Therapeutic recommendation	Classification of recommendation ^c	Other Considerations
CYP2C19 ultrarapid metabolizer	Increased clopidogrel active metabolite formation; lower on-treatment platelet reactivity	No recommendation	No recommendation	
CYP2C19 rapid metabolizer	Normal or increased clopidogrel active metabolite formation; normal or lower on-treatment platelet reactivity	No recommendation	No recommendation	
CYP2C19 normal metabolizer	Normal clopidogrel active metabolite formation; normal on-treatment platelet reactivity	If considering clopidogrel, use at standard dose (75 mg/day)	Strong	
CYP2C19 likely intermediate metabolizer	Reduced clopidogrel active metabolite formation; increased on-treatment platelet reactivity; increased risk for adverse cardiac and cerebrovascular events	Consider an alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitor at standard dose if clinically indicated and no contraindication	Moderate ^d	Alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitors not impacted by CYP2C19 genetic variants include ticagrelor and ticlopidine. Prasugrel is contraindicated in patients with a history of stroke or TIA ^e
CYP2C19 intermediate metabolizer	Reduced clopidogrel active metabolite formation; increased on-treatment platelet reactivity; increased risk for adverse cardiac and cerebrovascular events	Consider an alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitor at standard dose if clinically indicated and no contraindication	Moderate	Alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitors not impacted by CYP2C19 genetic variants include ticagrelor and ticlopidine. Prasugrel is contraindicated in patients with a history of stroke or TIA ^e
CYP2C19 likely poor metabolizer	Significantly reduced clopidogrel active metabolite formation; increased on-treatment platelet reactivity; increased risk for adverse cardiac and cerebrovascular events	Avoid clopidogrel if possible. Consider an alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitor at standard dose if clinically indicated and no contraindication	Moderate ^d	Alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitors not impacted by CYP2C19 genetic variants include ticagrelor and ticlopidine. Prasugrel is contraindicated in patients with a history of stroke or TIA ^e
CYP2C19 poor metabolizer	Significantly reduced clopidogrel active metabolite formation; increased on-treatment platelet reactivity; increased risk for adverse cardiac and cerebrovascular events	Avoid clopidogrel if possible. Consider an alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitor at standard dose if clinically indicated and no contraindication	Moderate	Alternative P2Y ₁₂ inhibitors not impacted by CYP2C19 genetic variants include ticagrelor and ticlopidine. Prasugrel is contraindicated in patients with a history of stroke or TIA ^e

^aNeurovascular disease includes acute ischemic stroke or transient ischemic attack, secondary prevention of stroke, or prevention of thromboembolic events following neurointerventional procedures, such as carotid artery stenting and stent-assisted coiling of intracranial aneurysms.

^bThe online CYP2C19 Allele Frequency Table provides phenotype frequencies for major race/ethnic groups, and the online CYP2C19 Diplotype-Phenotype Table provides a complete list of possible diplotypes and phenotype assignments.^{8,9}

^cRating scheme described in the **Supplementary Material** online.

^dThe strength of recommendation for "likely" phenotypes are the same as their respective confirmed phenotypes. "Likely" indicates the uncertainty in the phenotype assignment, but it is reasonable to apply the recommendation for the confirmed phenotype to the corresponding "likely" phenotype.

^eGiven limited outcomes data for genotype-guided anti-platelet therapy for neurovascular indications, selection of therapy should depend on individual patient treatment goals and risks for adverse events.

Source: CPIC guidelines. Dosing recommendations for clopidogrel dosing based on genotype for adult patients. (This table is taken for training purpose from Clinical Pharmacogenetic Implementation Consortium (CPIC) Guideline for Pharmacogenetics-Guided Clopidogrel Dosing: 2022 Update available at <https://files.cpicpgx.org/data/guideline/publication/clopidogrel/2022/35034351.pdf>)

DPYD based dose predictions: **Homework.**

Table 1. Assignment of likely DPD phenotypes based on DPYD genotypes

Likely phenotype	Activity score ^a	Genotypes ^b	Examples of genotypes ^c
DPYD normal metabolizer	2	An individual carrying two normal function alleles.	c.[=];[=], c.[85T>C];[=], c.[1627A>G];[=]
DPYD intermediate metabolizer	1 or 1.5	An individual carrying one normal function allele plus one no function allele or one decreased function allele, or an individual carrying two decreased function alleles.	c.[1905+1G>A];[=], c.[1679T>G];[=], c.[2846A>T];[=]; c.[1129-5923C>G];[=] ^d ; c.[1129-5923C>G];[1129-5923C>G] ^d ; c.[2846A>T];[2846A>T]
DPYD poor metabolizer	0 or 0.5	An individual carrying two no function alleles or an individual carrying one no function plus one decreased function allele.	c.[1905+1G>A];[1905+1G>A], c.[1679T>G];[1679T>G], c.[1905+1G>A];[2846A>T] c.[1905+1G>A]; [1129-5923C>G]

Notes:

ISSCP 2024 Report - Annexure

Plate layout

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A												
B												
C												
D												
E												
F												
G												
H												

Schedule and plan for Workshop 3: Exome sequencing analyses

Session overview

While genomics is being applied in most clinical settings these days for the diagnosis, prognosis and precise management of diseases, genetic variants that impact drug response also need to be considered while making healthcare decisions. Clinical adoption of findings from pharmacogenomics research can lead to better treatment outcomes for patients through improved medication safety and efficacy. In this workshop, we would be providing you with the basic knowledge on the concepts of clinical utility and implementation of pharmacogenomic studies.

Number of participants expected: ~20

Who should attend the workshop?

Clinicians, Clinical Geneticists and Genetic Counselors, Undergraduate and postgraduate Medical and life science students and students from pharmacology background.

Learning Objective

The objective of the workshop is to provide a basic understanding of pharmacogenomics and types of genetic variants associated with drug dosage and cause adverse drug reactions and how to perform a pharmacogenomic variant analysis and interpret pharmacogenomics reports.

Expected Outcomes

The workshop would provide a broad overview of what is pharmacogenomics and how a basic pharmacogenomic variant analysis is performed. The workshop would also enlighten the participants to understand and interpret a pharmacogenomics report and help them implement pharmacogenomics into clinical practice.

Technical/any other requirements for the workshop

Seating arrangement
Microphone and Speaker Systems
Overhead projector
Internet access for the hands on exercise

Session details

Lecture I: Basics of pharmacogenomics

The session would introduce the basic concepts of genomics and pharmacogenomics, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, and how genetic variants can impact the drug dosage and cause adverse drug reactions (ADRs).

Lecture II: Variant Annotation & Star Alleles

The session would provide an overview of the types of genetic variants, functional annotation, star alleles and genotype-phenotype assignment.

Lecture III & Hands-on I: Pharmacogenomics resources

This session would introduce the databases and resources (PharmGKB; DrugBank; CPIC) through which participants can explore pharmacogenomic information associated with various drugs.

Lecture IV: Genetic testing and Interpreting PGx reports

The session would provide an overview of the types of genetic testing available for pharmacogenomics and teach how to interpret a pharmacogenomics report.

Hands-on II - PGx variant analysis (30 minutes)

The hands-on session would introduce tools through which participants can perform pharmacogenomic variant analysis from a variant calling format file and generate a report.

Lecture V & Hands-on III: Understanding phenoconversion

This session would introduce the participants to a phenoconversion tool where they can generate a report that provides recommendations for medications based on the patient's genotype and their current medications.

Lecture VI: PGx case reports

The session would provide a broader understanding of pharmacogenomics in clinical practice through discussion of a few clinical case reports.

Report on the execution and feedback on the workshops

WORKSHOP 1 : During the ISSCP 2024 Workshop on Population PK Analysis, we utilized **Monolix** and **PKSim** software to conduct a series of simulations exploring the pharmacokinetic interactions between itraconazole (ITZ) and midazolam (MDZ), as well as the impact of liver impairment and genetic variability on MDZ metabolism. These software tools enabled us to model complex drug interactions and physiological conditions, providing insights into how drug-drug interactions (DDIs) and individual patient characteristics influence drug behavior in the body.

The primary focus of the simulations was to assess the potential DDI between ITZ, a potent CYP3A4 inhibitor, and MDZ, a substrate of CYP3A4. Using the simulation capabilities of both Monolix and PKSim, we were able to model ITZ's inhibitory effect on CYP3A4, leading to reduced metabolism of MDZ and an increase in its plasma concentrations. ITZ was identified as the **perpetrator** of the DDI, inhibiting the CYP3A4 enzyme, while MDZ was the **victim** of this interaction due to its dependence on CYP3A4 for clearance. The simulations showed that this interaction resulted in elevated **Cmax** and **AUC** for MDZ, which is crucial for understanding the clinical implications of such interactions.

In addition to the DDI simulation, we explored the effects of **liver impairment** (specifically Child-Pugh C) and **genetic variability** (e.g., CYP3A4*22 polymorphism) on MDZ metabolism. By adjusting CYP3A4 expression profiles in the Monolix and PKSim models to reflect these conditions, we observed that reduced CYP3A4 activity in both liver impairment and genetic subpopulations led to slower metabolism of MDZ, resulting in higher systemic exposure and prolonged elimination. These simulations emphasized the importance of considering individual patient factors, such as liver function and genetic makeup, when predicting drug behavior and determining optimal dosing regimens.

The use of Monolix and PKSim software provided a robust platform for modeling and simulating these complex pharmacokinetic scenarios. These tools allowed for a detailed understanding of how DDIs, liver impairment, and genetic variability can influence the pharmacokinetics of drugs like MDZ. Ultimately, the workshop highlighted the value of these software tools in supporting personalized medicine approaches, where drug dosing can be tailored to individual characteristics to optimize therapeutic outcomes and minimize the risk of adverse effects. By familiarizing ourselves with Monolix and PKSim, we gained practical experience in using advanced population pharmacokinetic models to inform drug development and clinical decision-making.

Feedback

A self-learning guide on PBPK and POP PK models has been circulated to all registered participants 3 working days prior to the workshop event. The post-test results exhibit a higher average score (5.8) compared to the pre-test (4.6), indicating an improvement in understanding after the workshop.

- For most questions, the most frequent answers align with the answer key in both tests; however, variations are more pronounced in the pre-test responses.
- Notably, questions related to:

- PBPK models (Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic models)
- Identifying non-pharmacokinetic models
show a significant increase in the frequency of correct answers in the post-test compared to the pre-test.
- Regarding the characteristics of traditional PK studies, there were 21 correct answers in the pre-test, which increased to 28 correct answers in the post-test, demonstrating significant improvement.

Overall, the workshop effectively enhanced participants' understanding, as evidenced by the higher average scores and reduced variability in the post-test results.

WORKSHOP 2: The RTPCR workshop was conducted by Dr. Uppugunduri and team from JIPMER and Dr. Lalitha Biswas and team at Amrita Center of nano science and molecular medicine. In the RT-PCR workshop, we analysed blood samples to detect genetic variations in *CYP2C19* and *DPYD*, critical genes for drug metabolism and toxicity. DNA was extracted from the blood using a kit, involving cell lysis, contaminant removal, and DNA elution. Using an RT-PCR kit, we prepared the reaction mix, including the extracted DNA, master mix (with Taq DNA Polymerase, dNTPs, MgCl₂, and buffer), and primers and probes specific to wild-type and mutant alleles. The RT-PCR machine was set for thermal cycling: initial denaturation of 95°C, cycling steps of denaturation (95°C), annealing (50–65°C), and extension (72°C), followed by final extension. Fluorescent signals coming from the probes were observed in real time to find amplification. Amplification curves and Ct values can be used to decide genotypes. Wild-type alleles exhibited fluorescence due to their probe, mutant alleles proved mutations, and dual fluorescence indicated heterozygous samples. Variations in *CYP2C19* are detected for drugs, such as clopidogrel, and *DPYD* mutation predicts fluoropyrimidine toxicity. This workshop highlighted how RT-PCR is necessary for the identification of pharmacogenetic variants, which holds the key to personalized medicines. It provided practical information on the technique's specificity in analysing DNA for a clinical application.

Feedback

The post-test results reveal a higher average score (9.05) compared to the pre-test (6.38), indicating an improvement in participants' understanding.

- The standard deviation of post-test scores (1.19) is notably lower than that of the pre-test (2.03), suggesting a more consistent level of comprehension among participants post-workshop.
- For most questions, the most frequent answers align with the answer key in both tests; however, variations are more prominent in the pre-test responses.
- Specific questions with notable improvement include:
 - The role of ethanol in DNA extraction
 - Essential components required for PCR completion
- Responses to questions about:
 - Definition of a genotype
 - True statements about DNA extraction methods
showed consistency, with the majority of participants choosing the correct options in both pre- and post-tests.

Overall, the workshop was successful in enhancing participants' understanding, as reflected by higher average scores and reduced score variability.

WORKSHOP 3: The works was started by a session on pharmacogenomics began with Dr. Bani Jolly introducing the concept and its significance in clinical practice. She emphasized the role of genetic variants in drug response and the growing need for personalized medicine. Following her talk, Sahana S presented on variant annotation and star alleles, explaining the different types of genetic variants and their annotations. She also discussed the importance of star alleles in pharmacogenomics. Sahana further introduced various pharmacogenomics resources and databases, demonstrating how they can be used to retrieve valuable information for clinical decision-making.

Dr. Jolly then delved into genetic testing methods for pharmacogenomics, highlighting the importance of interpreting pharmacogenomics reports to assess clinical relevance. Dr. Ambily Sivadas followed with a discussion on phenoconversion, explaining how this phenomenon can affect drug response and the application of pharmacogenomics in improving patient outcomes. She also presented case reports on the practical use of pharmacogenomics, sparking discussion among the attendees who shared their experiences.

Dr. Vinod Scaria led an open discussion on the challenges and opportunities of implementing pharmacogenomics in India. The group recognized the need for a national pharmacogenomics network and explored the potential benefits of such an initiative. The attendees agreed to form a working group to develop guidelines for pharmacogenomics implementation in India. They also decided to explore the creation of a national network to promote research and clinical application. The group plans to reconvene in the next two months to discuss these next steps.

Feedback

- For the question "What is the highest level of evidence in PharmGKB?", correct responses increased from 58% in the pre-test to 94% in the post-test, showing significant improvement.
- For the question "What information does PharmGKB offer?", the correct response rate rose from 75% in the pre-test to 100% in the post-test, demonstrating a clear improvement.
- However, the most frequently missed question in both pre-test and post-test was "Which of the following is NOT an ethical issue raised by pharmacogenetic testing?"
- Overall, participants demonstrated a better grasp of pharmacogenomics concepts, particularly in understanding the integration of genomics and pharmacology.

In summary, the workshop effectively improved participants' knowledge, as evidenced by increased accuracy and improved response rates in the post-test results.